

Both Java and JavaScript are commonly used web technologies. The similarities between their names often make beginners feel that JavaScript and Java are related. Java is an object-oriented, concurrent, and class-based, general purpose programming language, whereas JavaScript is an interpreted programming language. JavaScript is used widely as a client-side scripting language along with HTML and CSS, while Java is used by developer to build desktop GUI applications, websites and Android mobile apps. So it is important for programmers to understand the similarities and differences between the two popular technologies.

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Similarities between Java and JavaScript

As a popular client-side scripting language, JavaScript makes it easier for programmers to enhance a website's user experience without putting additional load on server. Code written in this language can run on major web browsers. Likewise, Java applets can also run on most web browsers. But many programmers avoid these applets due to security and compatibility issues.

Java is used by developers for creating a wide variety of client-server web applications. The programming language runs smoothly on several web servers including Apache Tomcat, WebSphere and JBoss. Despite being used widely as a client-side scripting language, JavaScript can also be used on the server side through Node.js. The massive popularity of Node.js has resulted in the emergence of several web servers powered by JavaScript.

Both Java and JavaScript have many libraries and frameworks. These frameworks and libraries help developers to reduce coding time significantly. Likewise, the developers also have option to reuse the code shared by communities to avoid writing any additional code. The libraries and frameworks further contribute towards making the web technologies popular and current.

Differences between Java and JavaScript

Normally, Java code is written using an integrated development environment (IDE), and then compiled into bytecode. No human being can read or understand the bytecode. The bytecode can be read and understood only by the Java Virtual Machine (JVM). On the other hand, JavaScript code is directly executed by the web browsers as written by the programmers. However, many programmers nowadays use tools to reduce the size of JavaScript files, and hence make the code unreadable.

The bytecode makes Java code platform-independent. The programmers can run the same code on different platforms without making any modification. But JavaScript code is executed directly by the web browsers. So it can be impacted by browser-compatibility issues. Often developers have to use JQuery (i.e., a JS library) to handle the browser incompatibility issues.

Java is a static typed language wherein the variable types are declared at the time of compilation. The variables can further accept values permitted for the [Convert JavaScript code to python](#) specific type. JavaScript, on the other hand is a dynamic typed language which allows programmers to declare variables with various value types including string, numeric and Boolean.

Working on a 100% object-oriented and class-based programming language, companies offering enterprise Java development services can use various OOP concepts to make the code reusable. This feature endears it to programmers who use it to create large and complex web applications. Despite supporting class and object, JavaScript is not fully object-oriented.

JavaScript supports closure in a manner similar to anonymous functions. The support enables programmers to pass a function as an argument to another function. But Java does not provide direct support to closures. The

developers have option to use anonymous class to simulate closure. However, Java 8 supports lambda expressions to make it easier for developers to pass function as an argument to another function.

While creating websites, developers cannot use JavaScript independently. Nowadays programmer use JS along with HTML5 and CSS3 to create modern websites and web applications. But Java is can be used independently as a programming language for building a variety of applications. At present, the programming language is used widely for development of web applications and mobile apps.

On the whole, JavaScript is not part of the Java platform. The programmers can use each of them independently based on the requirements of individual projects. However, Java SE 8 is designed with Nashorn Javascript Engine, which enables developers to run dynamic JavaScript code natively on the Java Virtual Machine. So the developers now have option to call JavaScript functions directly from Java code.

The Computer programming language CHIP-8 was originally developed by a Design Engineer by the name of Joe Weisbecker at RCA Labs, USA (1975-76). It's reason for being was simply to allow users of low cost Microcomputers to write there own Video Games without the complication of having to deal with lower level Machine code.

The programmer used a Hexadecimal Keypad to input data. The keypad typically produces Row and Column signal lines that are capable of being scanned by the Computer to determine which Keys were pressed. This method of programming was a significant step up from Binary coding which was very tedious to enter, and required a deep understanding of the Microprocessors internal architecture.

The first computer to have CHIP-8 resident was RCA's COSMAC VIP.

CHIP-8 is an Interpreter based language, and is usually found in ROM (Read Only Memory), within the Processors Memory Map. Because of this it can be termed - the Computers Operating System (CHIPOS).

The Vintage limitations of its use are - a graphics screen of only 64x32 pixel resolution, with a small program addressing space of only 4K bytes. This is due to the 12 bit width of the Memory Pointer - Register I.

Other highlights:

Monochrome Graphic display. Color was not initially supported.

The Users program resides in RAM (Random Access Memory) starting at address 0200 Hex.

Each programming Statement is two bytes in length (4 Hex digits).

The Instruction Set Consists of 33 Instructions.

There are 16 one byte variables - V0 to VF which can be modified using a variety of arithmetic/logic, and conditional branch instructions.

Worth repeating - The Memory Pointer (Register I) is 12 bits in length, thus giving an addressing range of 4K

bytes. A big limitation by today's standards.

Machine code programs can be called within CHIP-8 programs.

The CHIP-8 Computer Screen is organized in X,Y format. X co-ordinates range from 0 to 63, and Y co-ordinates range from 0 to 31. Co-ordinate 0,0 is at the top left side of the Screen.

Here is an example of CHIP-8 code that amplifies the simplicity of how a character can be written to the Screen:

Like all CHIP-8 programs, this program starts at address 0200 Hex -

VA=0

VB=0

I=210

SHOW 5 @ VA,VB

STOP

At Address 210 Hex is the data - F0,10,F0,80,F0,00

When run, this program will write the number 2 to the Screen, at Co-ordinate 0,0.